

DETECTION OF MACROPHAGE POLARIZATION IN GESTATIONAL PYELONEPHRITIS USING CD68 AND CD163 MARKERS

Tojiboev Temur Topvoldi o'gli

assistant, Andijan state medical institute

Adashbekova Muslima Nodirbek qizi

assistant, Andijan state medical institute.

Mamataliyev Avazbek Ruziboyevich

PhD in Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Andijan State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16716564>

Relevance of the issue

Gestational pyelonephritis is one of the most common nephrological complications during pregnancy, significantly affecting the general condition of the pregnant woman and the development of the fetus. Inflammation plays a central role in the pathogenesis of this disease, and its systemic analysis is crucial for understanding the specific immune responses associated with pregnancy. Macrophages are among the main effector cells in inflammatory processes and can polarize into M1 (pro-inflammatory) and M2 (anti-inflammatory) phenotypes. Detection of macrophage polarization using immunohistochemical markers such as CD68 and CD163 provides deeper insight into the pathogenesis of gestational pyelonephritis.

Objective

To assess the degree of macrophage polarization using CD68 and CD163 markers in cases of gestational pyelonephritis and to evaluate the impact of these changes on inflammation and fibrotic processes.

Materials and Methods

Kidney tissue samples (n=42) obtained from autopsies of pregnant women who died between 2020 and 2023 were analyzed. The cases were divided into primary and recurrent gestational pyelonephritis groups. Immunohistochemical analyses were performed using CD68 and CD163 markers. The number of positively stained macrophages per slide was counted, and statistical analysis was conducted (p<0.05 was considered significant).

Results

The study revealed macrophage polarization in the kidney tissues of patients with gestational pyelonephritis as determined by CD68 and CD163 expression. CD68 expression indicated a high level of general macrophage infiltration, confirming the intensity of the inflammatory process. Additionally, CD163-positive macrophages were predominantly located in fibrotic areas, suggesting a shift toward the M2 macrophage phenotype. The increase in M2

macrophages around nephrons is likely associated with tissue remodeling and interstitial fibrosis.

Moreover, differences were observed in the expression patterns of CD68 and CD163 between primary and recurrent pyelonephritis cases. In recurrent cases, CD163 expression was more prominent, indicating deeper progression of fibrotic changes. These findings suggest that, within the immunological context of pregnancy, CD68 and CD163 markers can provide valuable insights into the duration and nature of the immune response in gestational pyelonephritis.

Conclusion

Macrophage polarization in gestational pyelonephritis has significant clinical relevance. The use of CD68 and CD163 markers enables evaluation of the stages of inflammation and fibrosis. In primary cases, M1 macrophages predominated, whereas in recurrent cases, an increase in M2 macrophages was observed, indicating intensified tissue remodeling and fibrotic activity. These data support the potential development of novel pathogenetically targeted therapies based on the modulation of macrophage polarization.

References:

1. Wang Y. et al. "Macrophage polarization in kidney disease," *Kidney Int.*, 2020.
2. Krenkel O., Tacke F. "Macrophages in health and liver disease," *Cell. Mol. Immunol.*, 2017.
3. Cormack J.R. "Urinary tract infection in pregnancy," *Obstet Gynecol Clin North Am.*, 2015.
4. Martinez F.O. et al. "The M1 and M2 paradigm of macrophage activation: time for reassessment," *F1000Prime Rep.*, 2014.
5. Gordon S. "Alternative activation of macrophages," *Nat Rev Immunol.*, 2003.
6. Sica A., Mantovani A. "Macrophage plasticity and polarization," *Trends Immunol.*, 2012.
7. Kim H. et al. "Immune regulation by CD163+ macrophages in inflammatory renal diseases," *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 2018.

